

PREVALENCE OF ALLERGIC DISEASES AMONG CHILDREN IN THE PRIARALYE REGION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12505855>

Relevance. Recently, the so-called "ecological theory" has taken one of the leading roles in the development of allergic diseases. In the Priaralye region, the number of various factors acting as active sensitizers of the body and contributing to changes in its immune reactivity has increased. It has been established that children are more susceptible to the influence of ecopathological factors, especially during critical periods of growth and development due to the immaturity of metabolic processes and the incomplete processes of cell proliferation and differentiation.

The aim of the study was to investigate the prevalence of allergic diseases among children residing in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Materials and Methods. A retrospective analysis of outpatient medical records of 319 girls and 388 boys born in 2003 and 2004 who reached the age of 14 at the time of the study was conducted. The prevalence of allergic diseases such as bronchial asthma (BA), allergic rhinitis (AR), and atopic dermatitis (AD) was studied. The results of the study were subjected to statistical analysis. The diagnosis of allergic diseases was made according to the International Classification of Diseases 10th revision based on the results of clinical and instrumental examination of patients, which included analysis of complaints and medical history data; physical examination; results of laboratory methods with additional determination of IgE levels; assessment of lung function. Lung function tests were performed using pneumotachometry on the Polyalyzer PA5-02 apparatus. During the study, indicators of patency of various bronchi (FEF, L/s) were determined.

Results. The analysis of the study showed that among adolescents, BA was 3.1%, AR - 5.19%, and AD - 1.91%. The frequency of bronchial asthma among them increased by 3.15% (twice), allergic rhinitis by 16.07% (4 times), and atopic dermatitis by 1.29% (1.68 times).

Despite the fact that in recent years there has been a stagnation in the indicators of allergic morbidity in children, their overall trend has a significant tendency to increase. An increase in total IgE was detected in 35% of children, and an increase in IgE levels was observed in 77% of children with an increase in the number of episodes of allergic diseases and the presence of foci of chronic infection. In conditions of increased pollution of the lower atmospheric layer in the region, the patency of various bronchial divisions in children was closely correlated with the chemical composition of the air. A correlation was found with atmospheric air pollution: with nitrogen dioxide ($r=0.58$) and dust ($r=0.53$).

A multifactorial assessment of environmental parameters negatively affecting children's health showed that the overall share of explained variance determining the contribution of environmental factors to children's morbidity is quite significant and reaches 68.4%. The remaining variance - 31.6% - is due to endogenous factors.

Conclusion. Impairment of the functional state of the bronchopulmonary system in children is highly informative markers of an unfavorable ecological situation in the Priaralye region and

serve as additional diagnostic and prognostic criteria for the action of adverse environmental factors.